

THE INFLUENCE OF NAGARI'S INSTITUTIONAL AND FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SUSTAINABLE NAGARI DEVELOPMENT IN WEST SUMATRA PROVINCE

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Abstract

This study aimed to look at the influence of Nagari institutions and financial management on the performance of sustainable Nagari development and to find a model of sustainable Nagari development in West Sumatra Province. The population of this study was Nagari in West Sumatra Province, which was selected by purposive random sampling so that 182 Nagari were selected in Padang Pariaman Regency and Agam Regency. Meanwhile, the number of respondents was 364 respondents. The research instrument used a closed questionnaire instrument with a Likert scale of 1 to 5. The analysis tool used is Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS), and hypothesis testing is carried out by a bootstrapping resampling method that allows the validity of distribution-free data, not requiring the assumption of normal distribution. The results showed that institutions have a significant effect on economic development in Nagari, institutions have a significant effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development, Nagari financial management has a significant effect on economic development, Nagari financial management has a significant effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development, economic development has a significant effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development, institutions also indirectly significant effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development mediated by economic development, and Nagari financial management has a significant indirect effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development through economic development.

Keywords: Sustainable village development, economic development, institutions, village financial management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development has become a keyword in development discourse, related to different definitions of meaning and interpretation. Sustainable development means "Development that can continue indefinitely or for a certain period (Stoddart, 2011). Structurally, the concept can see as an expression consisting of two words, "sustainable" and "development." These two words can define variously from different points of view. The concept of sustainable development has also been viewed from different angles, leading to many definitions. Although definitions abound concerning sustainable development, the most frequently cited definition of the concept is the one proposed by the Brundtland Commission Report (Schaefer & Crane, 2005). The report defines sustainable development as "development that meets the needs of the current generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs."

Furthermore, (Iskandar, 2020) mentioned that there are 13 (thirteen) that are measures of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of villages, namely villages without poverty, villages without hunger, villages that care about health, quality village education, involvement of

village women, villages worthy of clean water and sanitation, clean and renewable energy villages, equitable village economic growth, infrastructure and village innovation as needed, villages without gaps, safe and comfortable village settlement areas, consumption and production of environmentally conscious villages, and villages responsive to change the climate.

Furthermore (Gorbenkova et al., 2018) mentioned that there are 3 (three) classifications of levels that encourage sustainable rural development, namely the first level includes 2 (two) factors, namely internal factors, and external factors. The second level consists of 5 (five) indicators, namely anthropogenic, social, economic, ecological, and administrative. The third level includes 13 (thirteen) indicators driving sustainable development: technological, built environment, social capital, social superstructure, living standards, economic variety, business activities, human Capital, budget structure, ecological environment, environmental impact, management structure, integration, and resources.

In measuring the economic performance of rural areas, then (Agarwal et al., 2009) examines the determinants of rural economic performance in the UK. There are 5 (five) indicators related to rural economic performance, namely: (1) Economic capital, (2) Human capital; (3) Social capital; (4) Cultural capital; and (5) Environmental Capital.

There are four levels of analytical frameworks in sustainable development (Silva et al., 2020), namely three types of Capital, namely (1) social Capital, which is divided into four categories, namely population, institutional, human relations, and information systems, with 7 (seven) sub-categories and 31 attributes; (2) Built Capital which is divided into two categories, namely economy and infrastructure systems, with ten sub-categories and ten attributes; and (3) Natural Capital which is divided into one category, namely resources with two sub-categories and four attributes. , as illustrated by (Silva et al., 2020) below :

Analytical framework for sustainable development (Silva et al., 2020)

Yustika (2012) mentioned that many experts had not examined the relationship between institutions and economic development. However, from these few studies, there is the following fact. Countries that have been grouped based on the availability of rules of the game of ownership rights, human capital investment, and economic performance show a strong relationship between the role of institutions in economic development.

The results of research by Clague et al. (1997) show that high initial per capita absorption does not provide guarantees for good economic performance in the long term. In contrast, countries whose initial per capita income is not very high have advantages in the institutional aspect, namely guaranteeing ownership rights, enforcing the contract system, and efficient public administration, resulting in superior economic performance.

Institutional is defined as the regulation of behavior generally accepted by members of social groups or rules that limit humanly devised behavior to establish a structure of political, economic, and social interaction (Halim, 2019). Through a series of histories, institutions that can minimize deviant human behavior have succeeded in creating order and reducing uncertainty in exchange.

2. METHODOLOGY

Sangadji (2010) mentioned that research methods are scientific ways to obtain data with a specific purpose and usefulness. Research methods are sciences that examine the provisions or rules regarding the methods used in research. This research is intended to provide explanations or is referred to as explanatory research or confirmatory research using quantitative data. Explanatory research is research that seeks to explain the causal relationship between research variables through the submission of hypotheses that have been formulated. This study was conducted to analyze the influence of Nagari financial management on institutions, the influence of Nagari financial management on economic development, the influence of institutions on Nagari economic development, the influence of institutions on the performance of sustainable Nagari development, the influence of economic development on the performance of sustainable Nagari development and the influence of Nagari financial management on the performance of sustainable Nagari development.

2.1 Population and samples

The province of West Sumatra is geographically located in the western part of the central part of the island of Sumatra. Geographically, it is divided into 2 (two) areas, namely the lowlands on the west coast and the volcanic plateaus formed by the Barisan hills. In addition, based on the residential area, the area in West Sumatra which is a minangkabau area in the upper 2 (two) areas, namely the luhak area consisting of 3 luhak known as luhak nan tigo, namely luhak tanah data (Tanah Datar Regency and Sijunjung Regency), luhak agam (Agam Regency), luhak limopuluah (Regency of Fifty Cities) and 2 rantau, namely rantau dihilia (east coastal area / riau) and rantau pasisie in mudiak (west coastal area / padang pariaman regency). Unit analysis in this study is the number of Nagari in West Sumatra Province, with the total population found in 11 (eleven) districts with a total Nagari population

of 802 (eight hundred and two). Another thing is based on the status of the district IDM value in 2020 is also divided into 2 (two) status levels, namely "developed" districts, as many as 5 (five) districts, namely Tanah Datar Regency, West Pasaman Regency, Agam Regency, Fifty Cities Regency and South Solok Regency and "developing" districts as many as 6 (six) districts, namely Sijunjung Regency, Dharmasraya Regency, Padang Pariaman Regency, Pasaman Regency, Pantai Selatan Regency and Solok Regency.

The sampling technique in this study carried out through multi-stage stratified random sampling, which is a way of random sampling of stratified ones with inhomogeneous elements and proportionally stratified from each population element taken randomly (Abdillah, 2015). Nagari is selected proportionally based on 4 (four) levels of Nagari development in the population area in 2021. The proportionally Nagari are Independent Nagari, Advanced Nagari, Developing Nagari, and Leftover Nagari. So that the size of the Nagari sample for each district refers to 4 (four) levels of clarity of Nagari development, namely Nagari in Padang Pariaman Regency with a sample of 102 Nagari with a description of 1 Independent Nagari, 29 Advanced Nagari, 68 Developing Nagari, and 4 Nagari left behind. Nagari in Agam District with a sample of 80 Nagari with 4 Independent Nagari, 48 Advanced Nagari, and 28 Nagari flourishing. So the total sample is 182 Nagari. Based on the population and sample calculations above, sampling was carried out randomly by revoking the lot against the list of names of the Nagari population that was the study's object according to the classification level. Meanwhile, the selected respondents representing the Nagari sample were the head of government of Nagari, represented by 2 (two) representatives of Nagari samples, namely Wali Nagari samples of 182 people, Secretary Nagari samples of 182 people, bringing the total number of respondents to 364 people.

2.2 Research Results

After tabulation of respondents' answer data obtained in this study, it was to measure the picture of respondents' responses to the questions in the questionnaire to obtain conclusions on the respondents' understanding of the problem to observe. Furthermore, calculations make on the average (Mean) of the respondent's answer score and the Respondent Achievement Rate (TCR). To see the criteria for respondents' achievement, 5 (five) TCR criteria and indexes to compile. These criteria are excellent criteria with a Respondent Achievement Rate (TCR) index of 86-100%, good criteria with a TCR index of 76-85%, criteria quite good with a TCR index of 66-75%, poor criteria with a TCR index of 50-65% and inadequate criteria with a TCR index of 1-49%. Furthermore, the average score (Mean) and criteria for the level of achievement of respondents against the statements prepared and against their indicators and variables answered by the respondents as described.

a. Description of Institutional Variables.

Furthermore, the following is to describe the mean value and the level of achievement of respondents from 4 (four) indicators of institutional variables, then the mean value and the level of respondent achievement are obtained from the institutional variable Mean value of 3.90, TCR value of 1436, TCR index value of 78.90%, with the respondent Achievement Level The criteria

are reasonable. The mean and level of achievement of respondents (TCR) from the institutional role variable (KL) as measured by 4 (four) indicators, namely indicators of the role of formal rules, the role of economic institutions, the role of social capital, and the role of social institutions are with a mean of 3.9. A TCR value of 78.90% with the respondent's achievement level criteria is good.

b. Description of Nagari Financial Management Variables.

Based on the description of the mean value and the level of achievement of respondents, 5 (five) indicators of the Nagari financial management variable. The mean value and the respondent's achievement level are obtained from the Nagari financial management variable, namely the Mean value of 4.70, the TCR value of 1712, and the TCR index value of 94.07%, with the Respondent Achievement Level.

The criteria were outstanding: The mean value and respondent achievement level (TCR) of the Nagari financial management variable (PKN) as measured by 5 (five) indicators. The indicators are namely indicators of financial planning quality, quality of financial organizing implementation, quality of financial administration, quality of financial reporting, and quality of financial accountability, with a mean of 4.70. A TCR value of 94.07% with the respondent's achievement level criteria is outstanding.

c. Description of Economic Development Variables

Furthermore, the following describes the mean value and the level of achievement of respondents of each indicator on the economic development variable. Based on the description of the mean value and the level of achievement of respondents. It has 5 (five) indicators of the economic development variable, the mean value, and the respondent's achievement rate is to obtain from the economic development variable Mean value of 3.90, the TCR value of 1405, the TCR index value of 77.20%, with the Respondent Achievement Level. The categorized of good Criteria based on The mean value and respondent achievement rate (TCR) of the economic development variable (PE) as measured by 5 (five) indicators. The indicator is the income level of the population, access to formal financial services, sources of income, employment opportunities, and regional openness, with a mean of 3.9 and a TCR value of 77.20% with the criteria of a good respondent achievement level.

d. Description of Sustainable Nagari Development Performance Variables

Furthermore, the following describes the mean value and the level of achievement of respondents of each indicator on the performance variables of sustainable development.

Based on the description of the mean value and the level of achievement of respondents, 10 (ten) indicators of the sustainable Nagari development performance variable. These indicators, the mean value, and the respondent's achievement level obtained from the sustainable Nagari development performance variable Mean value of 4.00, TCR value of 1467, and TCR index value of 80.60%, with the Respondent's Achievement Level Criteria being good. From the results of processing research data, it is known that the mean value and level of respondent achievement (TCR) from the Variable Sustainable Nagari Development Performance (KPNB).

While the outer model measurement model is as follows:

<p>Exogenous Latent Variables (ξ 1)</p> <p>$X1 = \lambda_{x1} \xi_1 + \delta_1$ $X2 = \lambda_{x2} \xi_1 + \delta_2$ $X3 = \lambda_{x3} \xi_1 + \delta_3$ $X4 = \lambda_{x4} \xi_1 + \delta_4$ $X5 = \lambda_{x5} \xi_1 + \delta_5$</p>	<p>Exogenous Latent Variable 2 (ξ 2)</p> <p>$X6 = \lambda_{x6} \xi_2 + \delta_6$ $X7 = \lambda_{x7} \xi_2 + \delta_7$ $X8 = \lambda_{x8} \xi_2 + \delta_8$ $X9 = \lambda_{x9} \xi_2 + \delta_9$</p>
<p>Endogenous Latent Variable 2 (η2)</p> <p>$y6 = \lambda_{y6} \eta_2 + \varepsilon_6$ $y7 = \lambda_{y7} \eta_2 + \varepsilon_7$ $y8 = \lambda_{y8} \eta_2 + \varepsilon_8$ $y9 = \lambda_{y9} \eta_2 + \varepsilon_9$ $y10 = \lambda_{y10} \eta_2 + \varepsilon_{10}$ $y11 = \lambda_{y11} \eta_2 + \varepsilon_{11}$ $y12 = \lambda_{y12} \eta_2 + \varepsilon_{12}$ $y13 = \lambda_{y13} \eta_2 + \varepsilon_{13}$ $y14 = \lambda_{y14} \eta_2 + \varepsilon_{14}$ $y15 = \lambda_{y15} \eta_2 + \varepsilon_{15}$</p>	<p>Endogenous Latent Variable 1 (η1)</p> <p>$y1 = \lambda_{y1} \eta_1 + \varepsilon_1$ $y2 = \lambda_{y2} \eta_1 + \varepsilon_2$ $y3 = \lambda_{y3} \eta_1 + \varepsilon_3$ $y4 = \lambda_{y4} \eta_1 + \varepsilon_4$ $y5 = \lambda_{y5} \eta_1 + \varepsilon_5$</p>

Information:

ξ	:	Ksi, exogenous latent variable
η	:	Eta, an endogenous latent variable
λ_x	:	Lamda x (small), loading exogenous latent variable factor
λ_y	:	Lamda y (small), endogenous latent variable loading factor
β	:	Beta (small), the coefficient of influence of endogenous variables on endogenous
γ	:	Gamma (small), the coefficient of influence of exogenous variables on endogenous
ζ	:	Zeta (minor), model error
δ	:	Delta (small), measurement error on exogenous latent variables
ε	:	Epsilon (small), measurement error on endogenous latent variables

f. Hypothesis Testing

To carry out hypothesis testing, the data analysis process using the Smart PLS application is carried out through the bootstrapping process. The results of the bootstrapping can see in figure 8 below:

Figure 3: Hiotesis Testing with bootstrapping analysis

Source: Results of data processing with SEM-PLS, 2021

g. Direct effect analysis

Hypotheses state to be accepted if the significance level is less than 0.05 or the t-value exceeds the critical value (Hair et al., 2010). The t-statistics value for the 5% significance level is 1.96. It needs to decide on the acceptance or rejection of a proposed hypothesis, and it is necessary to test the hypothesis using bootstrapping in the SEM-PLS software. Based on the results of structural model testing (inner model), hypothesis tests can carry out, which include t-statistics and parameter coefficients. To determine whether a hypothesis is acceptable or should be rejected, among others, by looking at the significance value between constructs, the t-statistical value, and the p-value. In the bootstrapping process in the intelligent PLS application, these three values will be displayed and will use in hypothesis testing in this study. Through the bootstrapping process, the path coefficient value obtained in table 7 below:

Table 7: Path Coefficient Value

Hypothesis	Variables/ Constructs	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T- Statistics	P Values	Result
H1	Institutional-> Economic development	0,405	0,399	0,077	5,233	0,000	Accepted
H2	Institutional -> Sustainable rural development performance	0,381	0,385	0,065	5,842	0,000	Accepted
H3	Rural financial management -> Economic development	0,246	0,264	0,080	3,088	0,002	Accepted
H4	Rural financial management -> Sustainable rural development performance	0,175	0,180	0,070	2,492	0,013	Accepted
H5	Economic development -> Sustainable rural development performance	0,222	0,216	0,077	2,891	0,004	Accepted

Source: Results of data processing with SEM-PLS, 2021

Based on the path coefficient results in table 7 above, it can see that the original sample value, p-value, and t- statistics value uses as a basis for making hypothesis decisions on whether they are accepted or rejected. The hypothesis is accepted if the t-statistics value $>$ the tablet or p-value < 0.05 .

Hypothesis 1 states an institutional influence on economic development in the Nagari of West Sumatra Province. Based on table 7, it can see that institutions have a significant effect on economic development in Nagari. The significant effect can be seen from the t-statistics value of $5.233 > 1.96$ or from the p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Meanwhile, the original sample value was 0.405 , which shows that the direction of the relationship between institutions and economic development is positive. Thus hypothesis 3 is acceptable.

Hypothesis 2 states an institutional influence on the performance of sustainable Nagari development in West Sumatra Province. Based on table 7, it can see that institutions have a significant effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development. This effect can be seen from the t-statistics value of $5.842 > 1.96$ or from the p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Meanwhile, the original sample value was 0.381 , which shows that the direction of the relationship between institutions and the performance of sustainable Nagari development is positive. Thus hypothesis 4 is acceptable.

Hypothesis 3 states that there is an influence of Nagari financial management on economic development in Nagari in West Sumate ra Province. Based on table 7, it can see that Nagari financial management has a significant effect on economic development. This effect of ec can be seen from the t-statistics value of $3.088 > 1.96$ or the p-value of $0.002 < 0.05$. Meanwhile, the original sample value was 0.246 , which shows that the relationship between Nagari financial management and economic development is positive. Thus hypothesis 1 is acceptable.

Hypothesis 4 states that there is an influence of Nagari financial management on the performance of Nagari development in West Sumatra Province. Based on table 7, Nagari's financial management significantly affects the performance of sustainable Nagari development. This effect can see from the t-statistics value of $2.492 > 1.96$ or from the p-value of $0.013 < 0.05$. Meanwhile, the original sample value was 0.175 , which shows that the direction of the relationship between Nagari financial management and the performance of sustainable Nagari development is positive. Thus hypothesis 2 is acceptable.

Hypothesis 5 states that there is an influence of economic development on the performance of sustainable Nagari development in West Sumatra Province. Based on table 7, economic development has a significant effect on the performance of sustainable development. The effect of performance can be seen from the t-statistics value f $2.891 > 1.96$ or from the p-value of $0.004 < 0.05$. Meanwhile, the original sample value is 0.222 , which shows that the direction of the relationship between economic development and sustainable Nagari development performance is positive. Thus hypothesis 5 is acceptable.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Analysis of the Direct Effect of Nagari's Financial Management on Economic Development.

It can be interpreted that the higher the quality value of Nagari Financial Management, the economic development of Nagari will also increase or the better the financial management of Nagari, the better the economic development of Nagari will be. The increase in one Nagari Financial Management unit will increase Economic Development by 24.6%. The magnitude of the parameter coefficient for the Nagari Financial Management (PKN) variable against the Economic Development (PE) variable is 0.246. It means that Nagari Financial Management has a positive influence on Economic Development in Nagari. Based on calculations using bootstrapping or resampling, the results of the Nagari financial management estimation coefficient test oneconomic development in Nagari are 0.246 with a calculated t value of 3.088 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.080. Then the P value is 0.002 < 0.05, so Hypothesis H1 that Nagari financial management has a significant direct effect on the economic development of Nagari in West Sumatra Province is statistically significant, so that H1 can be accepted.

It turns out that Nagari in West Sumatra, whose Nagari financial management is good, economic development in Nagari is also good. It turns out that from this research, all elements of Nagari's financial management have an impact on economic development in Nagari. This financial management element can increase economic development in Nagari, assuming that other influencing factors are constant. The law has placed the village as the spearhead of development and improving the community's welfare. Villages give adequate authority and sources of funds to manage their potential to improve the economy and the community's welfare. Ryan (2018) states that the village represents the smallest legal community unity that has existed to develop along with the history of community life. Village finance is all rights and obligations in organizing village government that can assess with money, including all forms of wealth related to village rights and obligations (Russian, 2018).

3.2 Analysis of the Direct Effect of Nagari Financial Management on the Performance of Sustainable Nagari Development

The magnitude of the parameter coefficient for the Nagari Financial Management (PKN) variable on the Sustainable Nagari Development Performance (KPNB) variable is 0.175, which means that there is a positive influence of Nagari Financial Management on the performance of Sustainable Nagari Development. It can be interpreted that the higher the quality value of Nagari Financial Management, the more Sustainable Nagari Development Performance will also increase or the better the Nagari financial management, the better the performance of sustainable Nagari development will also be. Improving one quality unit of Nagari Financial Management will increase the value of Sustainable Nagari Development Performance by 17.5%. Based on calculations using bootstrapping or resampling, the results of the Nagari financial management estimation coefficient test on sustainable Nagari development performance are 0.175 with a calculated t value of 2.492 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.070. So the P value is 0.013 < 0.05, so the H2 hypothesis that Nagari financial management

has a significant effect directly on the performance of sustainable Nagari development in West Sumatra Province is statistically significant, so H2 can be accepted.

From the findings, it turns out that in Nagari in West Sumatra, whose Nagari financial management is good, the performance of sustainable Nagari development is also good. The performance of sustainable Nagari development is because Nagari's financial management starts with many factors. These factors are quality planning, the implementation of financial organizing is exemplary, the quality of financial administration is also good, accompanied by good financial reporting, and the quality of financial accountability of Nagari is also good. From this research, it turns out that all elements of the Nagari financial management impact the performance of sustainable Nagari development, assuming that the other factors influencing factors are constant.

This factor is in line with the opinion of Deaton et al. (1992), the capital aspect as a concept of rural development through three approaches that are critical issues of rural development, namely

1. The capital needs of rural development from the supply-side analysis side,
2. The existence of policies that support the interaction between capital mobility and taxation for rural development,
3. The influence of globalization in capital formation for rural development.

Rural development should apply the principles of transparency (openness), participatory can enjoy by the community, and can account for (accountability and sustainability). Village Development aims to improve the welfare of the community and the quality of human life and poverty reduction through the provision of basic needs fulfilment, construction of facilities and infrastructure, development of local economic potential, and sustainable use of natural resources and the environment.

3.3 Analysis of the Direct Influence of Institutions on Economic Development

The magnitude of the parameter coefficient for the Institutional variable (KL) against the Economic Development (PE) variable is 0.405, which means there is a positive influence of institutions in Nagari on economic development in Nagari. It can be interpreted that the higher the institutional value, the economic development in Nagari will also increase or the better the role of institutions, the better the economic development of Nagari will also be. The increase in one institutional unit will increase Nagari's economic development by 40.5 %. Based on calculations using bootstrapping or resampling, the institutional estimation coefficient test results on economic development in Nagari are 0.405 with a calculated t-value of $5.233 > 1.96$ and a standard deviation of 0.077. So, the P value is $0.000 < 0.05$, so the H3 hypothesis that the role of institutions has a significant direct effect on the economic development of Nagari in West Sumatra Province is statistically significant so that H3 can be accepted.

It turns out that Nagari in West Sumatra, whose institutional role in Nagari is good, economic development in Nagari is also good. The development of Nagari is because the role of institutions in Nagari begins with a formal rule. The formal rules are economic institutions that

play a role and develop well, social capital can be put to good use, and social institutions are also running and playing a good role. It turns out that from this research, all elements of the institutions in Nagari have a significant impact on improving the economy in Nagari. This improvement can increase the performance of economic development in Nagari, assuming other influencing factors are constant.

Yustika (2012) mentions that the problem of financial institutions in rural areas can identify in 3 (three) aspects. First is the problem of access to credit. The characteristics of rural communities with a small business scale cause them not to have enough assets to use as collateral. As a result, their credit access to formal financial institutions has become severely limited. Second, rural communities' very low bargaining and information positions make them vulnerable to manipulation practices from formal and semi-formal financial institutions. The forms of manipulation vary. For example, the imposition of interest rates higher than government policies or the provision of credit that is very late interferes with planned business. Thirdly, asymmetric information of the lender towards the borrower. Every formal financial institution has limitations in recognizing the economic and business capabilities of any behavior in rural areas, so they tend to be cautious in disbursing credit. At that point, informal financial institutions come in to fill the limitations that formal financial institutions cannot reach.

3.4 Analysis of the Direct Influence of Institutions on the Performance of Sustainable Nagari Development

The magnitude of the parameter coefficient for the Institutional variable (KL) against the Nagari Development Performance variable (KPNB) is 0.381, which means that there is a positive institutional influence on the performance of sustainable Nagari development. It can be interpreted that the higher the institutional value, the more sustainable Nagari development performance will also increase or the better the institutional role, the better the performance of sustainable Nagari development will also be. The increase in one institutional unit will increase the performance value of sustainable development by 38.1%. Based on calculations using bootstrapping or resampling, the institutional estimation coefficient test on the performance of sustainable Nagari development are 0.381 with a calculated t-value of 5.842 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.065. Then the P value is 0.000 < 0.05. Hypothesis H4, that the role of institutions has a significant effect directly on the performance of sustainable Nagari development in West Sumatra Province, is statistically significant so that H4 can be accepted.

Based on the results of this study, it finds that Nagari in West Sumatra, whose institutions in Nagari are good, the performance of sustainable Nagari development in Nagari is also significant. It is because the institutional aspect turns out to have a significant role in supporting the performance of sustainable Nagari development. In Nagari, where the performance of sustainable Nagari development tends to be poor, the institutional role is not going well either. It turns out that from this research, all elements of the institution can affect the performance of sustainable Nagari development. It means that if the institution runs well, the performance of sustainable Nagari development will also be good, assuming that other influencing factors are constant. Mulyanto (2014) states that in measuring the progress of village development, 9

(nine) indicators. These indicators are (1) Apparatus capacity and reach of public services; (2) The wealth and finances of the village; (3) Village economic facilities; (4) Transportation and telecommunications facilities; (5) Institutional and community participation; (6) Community welfare; (7) Community education; (8) Public health; and (9) Family welfare. From this opinion, it can be seen that institutions affect the performance of sustainable Nagari development.

3.5 Analysis of the Direct Effect of Economic Development on the Performance of Sustainable Nagari Development.

The magnitude of the parameter coefficient for the Economic Development (PE) variable against the Nagari B sustainable Development Performance variable (KPNB) is 0.222, which means that PE has a positive influence on the KPNB. It can be interpreted that the higher the PE value, the higher the KPNB value, or the better the economic development of Nagari, the better the performance of sustainable Nagari development will also be. The increase in one PE unit will increase the KPNB value by 22.2 %. Based on calculations using bootstrapping or resampling. The test result of the pe coefficient of estimation β_1 against KPNB is 0.222 with a calculated t value of $2.891 > 1.96$ and a standard deviation of 0.077. So, the P value is $0.004 < 0.05$, so the H5 hypothesis that Nagari economic development has a significant effect directly on the performance of sustainable Nagari development in West Sumatra Province is statistically significant, so H5 can be accepted.

Based on the results of this study, it turns out that Nagari in West Sumatra, where economic development in Nagari is good, the performance of sustainable Nagari development in Nagari is also significant. The economic development of Nagari starts with good income of the population, open access to formal financial services, availability of good sources of Nagari income, opening up employment opportunities in Nagari and openness of the Nagari area. It turns out that from this research carried out, all elements of economic development have an impact on improving the performance of sustainable Nagari development in Nagari in West Sumatra Province. If it is assumed that other influencing factors are constant, then the elements of sound economic development will result in good development performance. Jamaluddin (2016) stated that sustainable development is not only concentrated on environmental issues but also included three scopes of policy, namely economic development, social development and environmental protection, which are the three pillars of sustainable development. Sustainable development should also be towards the eradication of poverty (economic goals), equitable and balanced (social targets) and high quality of environmental life (environmental targets).

3.6 Analysis of The Indirect Effect of Institutions on The Performance of Sustainable Nagari Development mediated by Economic Development

The magnitude of the parameter coefficient for the Institutional variable (KL) on the Performance of Sustainable Nagari Development (KPNB) through Economic Development (PE) is 0.099, which means that there is an indirect positive influence of KL on KPNB through PE. The higher the value of KL, the value of KPNB through PE will also increase or the better the role of institutions, the performance of sustainable development through

economic development will also be better. The increase in one KL unit will increase the Nilai KPNB through PE by 9.9%. Based on calculations they are using bootstrapping or resampling, the test results of the coefficient of estimation of KL through KPNB through PE are 0.099 with a calculated t value of $2.309 > 1.96$ and a standard deviation of 0.039. So the P value is $0.021 < 0.05$, so hypothesis H6 that the role of institutions has a significant indirect effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development through Nagari economic development in West Sumatra Province is meaningful or statistically significant H6 can be accepted.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

institutions have a significant effect on economic development in Nagari, institutions have a significant effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development, Nagari financial management has a significant effect on economic development, Nagari financial management has a significant effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development, economic development has a significant effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development, institutions also indirectly significant effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development mediated by economic development and Nagari financial management has an indirect significant effect on the performance of sustainable Nagari development through economic development.

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